

Thermodynamic modeling with uncertainty quantification using the modified quasichemical model in quadruplet approximation: Implementation into PyCalphad and ESPEI

Jorge Paz Soldan Palma,^a Rushi Gong,^a Brandon J. Bocklund,^b Richard Otis,^c Max Poschmann,^d
Markus Piro,^d Yi Wang,^a Tatiana G. Levitskaia,^e Shenyang Hu,^e Hojong Kim,^a Shun-Li Shang,^{a,*}
and Zi-Kui Liu^a

^a Department of Materials Science and Engineering, The Pennsylvania State University, University
Park, PA 16802, USA

^b Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Livermore, CA 94550, USA

^c Engineering and Science Directorate, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of
Technology, Pasadena, CA 91109, USA

^d Faculty of Energy Systems and Nuclear Science, Ontario Tech University, Oshawa, ON, Canada

^e Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, PO Box 999, Richland, WA 99352, USA

*Corresponding author. E-mail address: sus26@psu.edu

Jorge → jorge.pazsoldanpalma@gmail.com

Rushi → rsgong@psu.edu

Brandon → bocklund1@llnl.gov

Max → Max.Poschmann@ontariotechu.ca

Markus Piro <Markus.Piro@ontariotechu.ca>

Yi → yuw3@psu.edu

Tatiana → Tatiana.Levitskaia@pnnl.gov

Shenyang → Shenyang.Hu@pnnl.gov

Hojong → huk29@psu.edu

ZKL → zx115@psu.edu

Otis, Richard → richard.otis@jpl.nasa.gov

Abstract:

The modified quasichemical model in the quadruplet approximation (MQMQA) considers the first- and the second-nearest-neighbor coordination and interactions, becoming one of the best models to describe short-range ordering in complex liquids such as molten salts, slag in metal processing, and electrolytic solutions. The present work implements the MQMQA into Python based open-source software PyCalphad for thermodynamic calculations using the CALPHAD approach. This endeavor facilitates the development of MQMQA-based thermodynamic database with uncertainty quantification (UQ) using the open-source software ESPEI. New database format XML (extensible markup language) has been proposed to extensively parse other standard database formats. Taking the KF-NiF₂ system as an example, we demonstrate the successful implementation of MQMQA through thermodynamic calculations of, e.g., Gibbs energy, equilibrium quadruplet fractions, and phase diagram, using PyCalphad, as well as database development with UQ using ESPEI. The present implementation indicates that the open-source PyCalphad/ESPEI could provide an accurate alternative to perform CALPHAD modeling for complex liquids with short-range ordering, making the MQMQA more accessible to the broad community.

1 Introduction

Computational thermodynamics via the CALPHAD modeling approach [1–3] is a key methodology to understand, predict, and optimize materials in terms of thermodynamic properties of individual phases – the building blocks for the materials of interest [4,5]. Precise predictions using the CALPHAD approach call for advanced models and accurate databases for all phases of involved. For example, thermodynamics is the key to understand critical features of molten salts used in the Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) [6], optimize fuel composition, and define safety margins, aiming to fulfill multiple requirements of molten salts, for example, i) low-melting temperature to decrease the risk of freezing and precipitation, ii) low vapor pressure at operating temperatures, iii) high heat capacity to store more energy, iv) thermodynamic stability, v) good solubility of fissile and fertile isotopes (e.g., ^{233}U , ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and/or ^{239}Pu), and vi) superior corrosion resistance [7,8].

Thermodynamic description of complex liquid of molten salts is mainly based on (i) the two-sublattice ionic liquid model, which can consider charge balance but cannot address the short-range ordering (SRO) [9], and (ii) the modified quasichemical model (MQM), which can describe SRO in molten salts [10,11]. As illustrated in Table 1, within the CALPHAD community the ionic model is mainly adopted by the TDB-(sub)community using the TDB format for thermodynamic database and the software tools of Thermo-Calc [12], OpenCalphad [13], Pandat [14], and PyCalphad/ESPEI [15,16], where the major databases developed are the Scientific Group Thermodata Europe (SGTE) molten salts database [17] and the Thermodynamics of Advanced Fuels – International Database (TAF-ID) [18]. The MQM and especially the MQM in the quadruplet approximation (MQMQA) are dominant models for molten salts, which are adopted

mainly by the DAT-(sub)community using the DAT ASCII format (as well as other encrypted formats [19]) for thermodynamic database and the software tools of FactSage [19] and Thermochemica [20], where the major databases developed are the commercial FTsalt [19] and the open Molten Salt Thermal Properties Database – Thermochemical (MSTDB-TC) [21]. Note also that both the TDB- and the DAT-(sub)communities are almost “isolated” due to the adoption of different database formats and especially different software packages (mainly the commercial codes of Thermo-Calc and FactSage); making it difficult to examine and update models and molten salts databases by the whole CALPHAD community. Relevant to the MQMQA – one of the best models for molten salts [10] – which was only implemented in the commercial software of FactSage [19] and the open-source software of Thermochemica [20]. Both software tools can perform thermodynamic calculations, while database development is not the focus of Thermochemica [20]. Notably the open-source software, OpenCalphad [13], is implementing the MQMQA, but currently it is not released to the public yet.

The present work aims to implement the MQMQA in Python-based open-source software packages of PyCalphad [15] for thermodynamic calculations and ESPEI [16] for database development, making the MQMQA more accessible to the broad community. Here, PyCalphad [15] is a Python library for designing thermodynamic models, calculating phase diagrams, and investigating phase equilibria using the CALPHAD method. ESPEI [16] is designed for inverse modeling of models and model parameters with PyCalphad as the computational engine. The present implementation of the MQMQA can take the benefits of PyCalphad and ESPEI, including, for example, i) benefits from the fast-growing Python language, ii) high throughput CALPHAD modeling, iii) development of thermodynamic database with less human input due to the adoption

of machine learning based Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) optimization, and iv) uncertainty quantification (UQ) for both models and model parameters.

In addition to the methodology and the implementation of the MQMQA (detailed in Sec. 2), using the KF-NiF₂ system as an example, we demonstrate (i) the capacities of PyCalphad for thermodynamic calculations (including the predicted Gibbs energy, enthalpy, entropy, quadruplet fractions, and phase diagram) by reading thermodynamic database in DAT format and especially the presently proposed XML (extensible markup language) format which is platform independent and programming language independent (see also Table 1); together with (ii) the capacities of ESPEI for database development and the resulting uncertainty quantifications (UQs) of thermodynamic properties (detailed in Sec. 3). These capacities indicate that the present implementation in PyCalphad and ESPEI contribute to unions in the CALPHAD community in terms of the MQMQA, besides the previous implemented models such as the sublattice model, the associate model, and the ionic model.

2 The MQMQA and its Implementation

2.1 The MQMQA

In the MQMQA, two sublattices are introduced in order to simultaneously account for the first nearest neighbors (FNN) and the second nearest neighbors (SNN) interactions in a solution. In molten salt systems, the two sublattices separate the cations from the anions. Furthermore, the present formalism considers the distribution of quadruplets (four constituents) rather than pairs (two constituents) [11,22]. Figure 1 illustrates how to visualize a quadruplet (A,B)(X,Y) in a two-

dimensional lattice and how they will be labeled based on their chemistry [23]. In a molten salt system, it is seen that the quadruplets consist of two cations and two anions. The quadruplets can be classified into three different categories (Figure 1), i.e., the unary quadruplets [A_2X_2 , B_2X_2 , A_2Y_2 , and B_2Y_2], the binary quadruplets [ABX_2 , ABY_2 , A_2XY , and B_2XY], and the reciprocal quadruplet [$ABXY$]. The SNN coordination number, which is a modeler-chosen parameter, is applied to reproduce the SRO compositions in a chemical system and represent the coordination of species in a melt. Based on Pelton's notations [11], for example, one can represent the SNN coordination number of A in the [$ABXY$] reciprocal quadruplet as $Z_{AB:XY}^A$. The condition of charge neutrality for this quadruplet is maintained as follows,

$$\frac{q_A}{Z_{AB:XY}^A} + \frac{q_B}{Z_{AB:XY}^B} = \frac{q_X}{Z_{AB:XY}^X} + \frac{q_Y}{Z_{AB:XY}^Y} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where q_i is the absolute charges of ion i ($= A, B, X, \text{ or } Y$).

Although the MQMQA [11] is different in many aspects with respect to such as the associate model and the regular model [1,2], the Gibbs energy of liquid as a function of temperature (T) and composition (x) can still be calculated by three contributions,

$$G^{Liquid} = G^{surface} - TS^{conf} + G^{Excess} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where $G^{surface}$ represents the reference surface energy, S^{conf} the configurational entropy, and G^{Excess} the excess Gibbs energy of liquid. The surface reference energy can be expressed by,

$$G^{surface} = \sum_{i=A,B} \sum_{\substack{j=A,B \\ j \geq i}} \sum_{\substack{m=X,Y \\ m \geq j}} \sum_{\substack{n=X,Y \\ n \geq m}} X_{ij:mn} G_{ij:mn}^o \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where $X_{ij:mn}$ represents the mole fraction of the specified quadruplet $[ijmn]$ and $G_{ij:mn}^o$ the standard Gibbs energy per mole of the specified quadruplet [11]. The configurational entropy can be approximately represented by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 -S^{conf}/R = & \sum_{i=A,B} X_i \ln X_i + \sum_{m=X,Y} X_m \ln X_m + \sum_{i=A,B} \sum_{m=X,Y} X_{i:m} \ln \left(\frac{X_{i:m}}{Y_i Y_m} \right) \\
 & + \sum_{i=A,B} \sum_{\substack{j=A,B \\ j \geq i}} \sum_{\substack{m=X,Y \\ m \geq j}} \sum_{\substack{n=X,Y \\ n \geq m}} X_{ij:mn} \ln \left(\frac{X_{ij:mn}}{f X_{i:m}^{e_1} X_{j:m}^{e_1} X_{i:n}^{e_1} X_{j:n}^{e_1}} \frac{Y_i^{e_2} Y_j^{e_2} Y_m^{e_2} Y_n^{e_2}}{Y_i^{e_2} Y_j^{e_2} Y_m^{e_2} Y_n^{e_2}} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{Eq. 4}$$

where X_i is the mole fraction of species i , $X_{i:m}$ the mole fraction of the pair $i:m$, and R the gas constant. The third term in the right side of Eq. 4 represents the contribution from the FNN, where Y_i is the coordination equivalent site fraction and can be calculated as follows,

$$Y_i = \frac{Z_i X_i}{Z_i X_i + Z_j X_j + \dots} \tag{Eq. 5}$$

Note that the third and the fourth term of Eq. 4 are based on two different derivations from Pelton [11]. The original formalism [23], which is labeled as SUBG in the software FactSage, kept ζ (a parameter that relates how many quadruplets emanate from a specific pair) as a constant value. However, the new formalism derived by Lambotte and Chartrand [24], denominated as SUBQ in FactSage, allows ζ to be a function of composition. This change results in a modified coordination equivalent site fraction, F_i ,

$$F_i = \sum_m X_{i:m} \tag{Eq. 6}$$

and replaces the Y_i term in Eq. 4. These two different formalisms affect the last term in the configurational entropy expression in Eq. 4 as well. The last term in Eq. 4 represents the

contribution from the SNN, where f is a factor/coefficient and it equals to 1 for unary quadruplets, 2 for binary quadruplets, and 4 for reciprocal quadruplet. Note that the exponents e_1 and e_2 in the denominator of the 4th term in Eq. 4 correspond to the symbols SUBG and SUBQ used by FactSage [19], with $e_1 = 1$ and $e_2 = 1$ for the case of SUBG; and $e_1 = 0.75$ and $e_2 = 0.5$ for SUBQ. It is derived the modified expression in SUBQ gives a more accurate approximation of the quadruplet concentration when a negative value such as -100 kJ per charge equivalent for exchange reactions in quadruplets is applied in the model [23,24]

The excess Gibbs energy G^{Excess} relates to the formation Gibbs energy of the quadruplet formations, $\Delta g_{quadruplet}^{ex}$. For example, the following reaction forms quadruplets,

where $\Delta g_{AB:X_2}^{ex}$ indicates the Gibbs energy change when forming the quadruplet $[ABX_2]$. If $\Delta g_{AB:X_2}^{ex} = 0$, the ideal random mixing occurs. If $\Delta g_{AB:X_2}^{ex} < 0$, the reaction of Eq. 7 takes place and the SRO with the $[ABX_2]$ SNN pairs is predominant [11]. Considering multicomponent systems, Pelton [11] indicated the necessity to describe multicomponent systems with appropriate interaction parameters and taking into account what chemical groups the elements of interest would belong to. In this case the variables $\xi_{ij:X_2}$ and $\chi_{12:X_2}$ are introduced to the excess Gibbs energy expression; where the $\xi_{ij:X_2}$ is defined as follows,

$$\xi_{ij:X_2} = Y_i + \sum_k Y_k \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where k is the component in the i - j - k system and j is the asymmetrical component. The $\chi_{12:X_2}$ is defined as follows,

$$\Delta\chi_{12:X_2} = \frac{\sum_{A=1,k} \sum_{B=1,k} (X_{AB:X_2} + \sum_{Y \neq X} 0.5 X_{AB:XY})}{\sum_{A=12,k,l} \sum_{B=12,k,l} (X_{AB:X_2} + \sum_{Y \neq X} 0.5 X_{AB:XY})} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where l is the component in the i - j - l system and i is the asymmetrical component. It should be noted that the terms regarding reciprocal quadruplets in Eq. 9 are only considered in the SUBQ category to improve interpolation contributions from the reciprocal quadruplets.

Through this approach by Pelton [11], one can study the interpolation effects based on the symmetrical and asymmetrical components in sub-ternary systems. By considering these variables, the expression of $\Delta g_{AB:X_2}^{ex}$ is,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta g_{AB:X_2}^{ex} = & \Delta g^o + \sum_{(i+j \geq 1)} \chi_{AB:X_2}^i \chi_{BA:X_2}^j g_{AB:X_2}^{ij} \\ & + \sum_{\substack{(i \geq 0) \\ (j \geq 0) \\ (k \geq 1)}} \chi_{AB:X_2}^i \chi_{BA:X_2}^j \left[\sum_l \frac{g_{AB(l):X_2}^{ijk} X_{l:X}}{Y_X} (1 - \xi_{AB:X_2} - \xi_{BA:X_2})^{k-1} \right. \\ & + \sum_m \frac{g_{AB(m):X_2}^{ijk} X_{m:X}}{Y_X \xi_{BA:X_2}} \left(1 - \frac{X_{B:X}}{Y_X \xi_{BA:X_2}} \right)^{k-1} \\ & \left. + \sum_n \frac{g_{AB(n):X_2}^{ijk} X_{n:X}}{Y_X \xi_{AB:X_2}} \left(1 - \frac{X_{A:X}}{Y_X \xi_{AB:X_2}} \right)^{k-1} + \sum_{Y \neq X} Y_Y (1 - Y_X)^{k-1} \right] \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where the first two terms in the right side are binary expressions and the rest terms describe ternary interactions with symmetrical and asymmetrical considerations for the components being mixed. The first of the three ternary interactions represents the scenario when either component k is the asymmetrical component or when all components are symmetrical. The second term is when the species B is the asymmetrical component in the system. The third term is when the species A is the asymmetrical component in the system. The final term represents a reciprocal ternary

interaction parameter to describe the interaction between [AB:X2] quadruplet when component Y is present.

2.2 Implementation of MQMQA into PyCalphad and ESPEI

Figure 2 shows the flow chart regarding the implementation of MQMQA into PyCalphad, where the new features of the present efforts are highlighted by green and the pre-existing features are highlighted by blue. The first step of implementation is reading in the database in different formats (see also Table 1), i.e., the DAT file in the FactSage/ChemSage (ASCII) format used by the DAT-(sub)community (including FactSage [19] and Thermochemica [20]), or the TDB format used by the TDB-(sub)community (including Thermo-Calc [12], OpenCalphad [13], Pandat [14], and PyCalphad/ESPEI [15,16]), or the XML format proposed by the present authors.

To support a unified, on-disk representation of CALPHAD-type databases that avoids implementing software-specific extensions to the *de facto* standard TDB and DAT formats, we propose a new database format using XML. Unlike the existing custom markup languages used in CALPHAD databases that require each software tool to develop bespoke implementations of non-standard, *ad hoc* syntaxes, XML is a well-established, standardized markup language that is human- and machine-readable. Virtually all programming languages have XML parsers implemented in their standard libraries or in common third-party libraries. To describe the domain-specific aspects, we use a declarative Relax NG-based schema [25] that uses XML syntax. The XML parser for PyCalphad is implemented as a separate plugin package called “PyCalphad-xml”, that provides function handles that are used by PyCalphad Database objects to read, write, and validate XML databases using the Relax NG schema provided by the PyCalphad-xml package.

The second step of implementation is to inform PyCalphad to perform equilibrium calculations (*cf.*, Figure 2) using the MQMQA or other models for a specific phase. It should be noted that the XML databases contain all information for phases, users do not have to specify models for the phases of study when using PyCalphad. Then, the MQMQA is fed into the computational engine of PyCalphad, which will perform equilibrium calculations with respect to all internal degrees of freedom [15]. Equilibrium is determined by Gibbs energy minimization [15]. Since ESPEI uses PyCalphad as its computational engine, the implementation of MQMQA into PyCalphad makes it possible for ESPEI to perform CALPHAD modeling using the MQMQA. Note also that we can use the features of ESPEI and PyCalphad for CALPHAD modeling using the MQMQA such as the UQs of model parameters and the MCMC for database development, see details in Sec. 1 as well as the discussion in the literature [15,16].

3 Demonstration of Equilibrium Calculations using PyCalphad

Using the NiF₂-KF database modeled by Ocadiz-Flores et al. [26] in terms of the MQMQA and the FactSage software, we validate the implementation of the MQMQA in PyCalphad [15,27] by performing equilibrium calculations. For the convenience of users, we also made a Jupyter Notebook as Supplemental Material to show the details of calculations.

Figure 3 shows the calculated Gibbs energy, entropy, and enthalpy of NiF₂-KF at 1600 K, which is in the liquid phase region, using the MQMQA in terms of PyCalphad. For the purpose of comparison, the Gibbs energies are calculated using both PyCalphad [15], Thermochemica [20] and FactSage [19]. Figure 3a shows that the Gibbs energy, entropy, and enthalpy from PyCalphad

agree well with those from predictions by both Thermochemica and FactSage, indicating the successful implementation of MQMQA into PyCalphad. To demonstrate the unique feature of PyCalphad, Figure 4 shows the Gibbs energy surface of NiF₂-KF liquid at 1600 K calculated using PyCalphad by sampling of the internal degrees of freedom (quadruplet fractions in the present case) [28]. It presents the overall surface at each composition consists of different configurations of quadruplet fractions and the respective energies that belong to them. Figure 5 is the calculated pseudobinary phase diagram of KF-NiF₂ in comparison with experimental data used to model this system by Ocadiz-Flores et al. [26]. It is seen that the phase diagram was correctly reproduced by PyCalphad, which is self-evident by the agreement with experimental data. It also illustrates that PyCalphad can correctly minimize the Gibbs energy and calculate phase equilibria. Figure 6 shows the predicted quadruplet fractions as a function of NiF₂ mole fraction, $x(\text{NiF}_2)$, at 1600 K for three quadruplets of [K₂F₂], [Ni₂F₂], and [KNiF₂] in the NiF₂-KF system. As it can be seen that the overall distribution of the [KNiF₂] quadruplet skews toward $x(\text{NiF}_2) = 0.38$, which relates to the composition with the maximum SRO ($x(\text{NiF}_2) = 0.333$) based on the coordination numbers chosen in the MQMQA, showing the bonding nature of species in NiF₂-KF.

4 Demonstration of thermodynamic modeling with UQ using ESPEI

In addition to equilibrium calculations by PyCalphad, ESPEI with the computational engine of PyCalphad can be used for the evaluation of model parameters using the implemented MQMQA with UQ [29]. Once the user provides a thermodynamic database with estimated values of adjustable parameters and datasets describing thermochemical and phase boundary data, parameters in the database can be simultaneously optimized using the MCMC method implemented in ESPEI [16]. The statistical distributions of the model parameters are evaluated

from the samples during MCMC optimization based on the Metropolis criteria [16]. In the present work, the excess Gibbs energy of liquid (i.e., $\Delta g_{AB:X_2}^{ex}$ in Eq. 10) were chosen as model parameters and remodeled to quantify uncertainty using a 95% uncertainty interval (or Bayesian credible intervals containing 95% of the invariant samples). During the modeling process by ESPEI/PyCalphad, the Markov chain values can be tracked and the MCMC steps were performed until all model parameters converged. Note that 8 chains were selected for each model parameter with a total of 800 iterations performed. For the convenience of users, we also made a Jupyter Notebook as Supplemental Material to show the details of CALPHAD modeling.

Similarly to those in Sec. 3, the KF-NiF₂ system modelled by Ocadiz-Flores et al. [26] were selected for the demonstration; where the input datasets (here, they are JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) files) with phase boundary data were used as constraints during the modeling process, see the data in Figure 5 or the JSON files in the Supplementary Materials. Figure 7 shows the evolution of chains during MCMC iterations indicated by log-probability changes for all the chains as a function of iterations. After around 20 MCMC iterations, the chains are converged to similar log-probabilities around -1.48×10^3 , indicating the convergence of MCMC optimization of model parameters. After MCMC of 800 steps, the modelled parameters values are listed in Table 2.

The uncertainty of thermodynamic properties can be quantified after CALPHAD modeling by MCMC using PDUQ (Phase Diagram Uncertainty Quantification) [29]. It relies on the PyCalphad for predicting thermodynamic properties of interest and ESPEI for Bayesian samples to leverage the distribution of model parameters and estimate uncertainties based on the estimated Gaussian distribution of input data [29]. As an example, Figure 8 shows the uncertainty of phase fractions

as a function of temperature with $x(\text{NiF}_2) = 0.32$ for the KF-NiF₂ system. The plot presents two different invariant reactions ($\text{KF} + \text{NiK}_2\text{F}_4 \rightarrow \text{liquid}$ and $\text{NiK}_2\text{F}_4 \rightarrow \text{NiKF}_3 + \text{liquid}$) and two two-phase regions ($\text{KF} + \text{NiK}_2\text{F}_4$ and $\text{NiKF}_3 + \text{liquid}$) before complete melting of the system is predicted. It shows that the eutectic reaction of 1075 K has the lowest uncertainty of the invariant reactions and the liquid + NiKF₃ region has the highest uncertainty based on the shaded region plotted. These results are expected since there was more data provided by the literature that validated the eutectic temperature of 1075 K than those to validate the liquidus temperature at $x(\text{NiF}_2) = 0.32$ [26,30,31].

The uncertainties of phase fraction increase from 1200 K to 1400 K, where the peritectic reaction “ $\text{NiK}_2\text{F}_4 \rightarrow \text{NiKF}_3 + \text{liquid}$ ” occurs (see also the phase diagram in Figure 5) then NiKF₃ and liquid two phases region. The shadow regions of NiKF₃ and liquid indicate that the liquidus temperature was predicted with an uncertainty from 1300 K to 1400 K at $x(\text{NiF}_2) = 0.32$. These uncertainty results are expected since small amounts of scattering occur in different experiments [26,30,31] when measuring this invariant reaction and liquidus.

As another example, Figure 9 displays the uncertainty of the Ni activity as a function of composition $x(\text{Ni})$ at 1800 K. The uncertainties of the activity at $x(\text{Ni}) = 0.2 - 0.25$ show higher values due mainly to least amounts of data points and greater scatter of temperatures measured. The present study has successfully shown that the user can apply UQ to study phase equilibria and thermodynamic properties after the MQMQA modeling for the first time.

5 Summary

The present work successfully implemented the modified quasichemical model in the quadruplet approximation (MQMQA) into the Python based open-source software PyCalphad. As a result of the PyCalphad implementation, it is now possible to use the open-source software ESPEI for parameter optimization and uncertainty quantification (UQ) for thermodynamic database development. Here, a new database format XML has been proposed to extensively parse other standard database formats. Using the KF-NiF₂ system as an example, we demonstrate the capacities of the implemented MQMQA to perform equilibrium thermodynamic calculations by PyCalphad, and database development together with UQ by ESPEI. The present predictions agree well with experimental or calculated results available in the literature, indicating the success of the implementation in PyCalphad/ESPEI. The present implementation hence provides an accurate alternative to perform CALPHAD modeling for complex liquids including molten salts, making the MQMQA more accessible to the broad community by eliminating various barriers such as the communication between the TDB and DAT formats of thermodynamic database within the CALPHAD community.

6 Acknowledgements

The authors at Penn State acknowledge the financial supports by the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) via Award No. DE-NE0008945. Part of this work was performed under the auspices of the U.S. DOE at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under Contract No. DE-AC52-07NA27344. B.B. acknowledges support from a NASA Space Technology Research Fellowship (NSTRF 80NSSC18K1168).

References:

- [1] H.L. Lukas, S.G. Fries, B. Sundman, *Computational Thermodynamics: The CALPHAD Method*, Cambridge University Press, 2007.
- [2] N. Saunders, A.P. Miodownik, *CALPHAD (Calculation of Phase Diagrams): A Comprehensive Guide*, Pergamon, Oxford; New York, 1998.
- [3] Z.-K. Liu, *First-Principles Calculations and CALPHAD Modeling of Thermodynamics*, *J. Phase Equilibria Diffus.* 30 (2009) 517–534. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11669-009-9570-6>.
- [4] Z. Liu, *Perspective on Materials Genome®*, *Chinese Sci. Bull.* 59 (2014) 1619–1623. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11434-013-0072-x>.
- [5] L. Kaufman, J. Ågren, *CALPHAD, first and second generation – Birth of the materials genome*, *Scr. Mater.* 70 (2014) 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2012.12.003>.
- [6] *Molten Salt Chemistry Workshop*, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, 2017. <https://www.ornl.gov/content/molten-salt-chemistry-workshop>.
- [7] O. Beneš, R.J.M. Konings, *Thermodynamic Calculations of Molten-Salt Reactor Fuel Systems*, in: *Molten Salts Chem.*, Elsevier, 2013: pp. 49–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-398538-5.00004-4>.
- [8] A.E. Danon, O. Muránsky, I. Karatchevtseva, Z. Zhang, Z.J. Li, N. Scales, J.J. Kruzic, L. Edwards, *Molten salt corrosion (FLiNaK) of a Ni–Mo–Cr alloy and its welds for application in energy-generation and energy-storage systems*, *Corros. Sci.* 164 (2020) 108306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2019.108306>.
- [9] M. Hillert, B. Jansson, B. Sundman, J. Ågren, *A two-sublattice model for molten solutions with different tendency for ionization*, *Metall. Trans. A.* 16 (1985) 261–266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02815307>.
- [10] T.M. Besmann, J. Schorne-Pinto, *Developing Practical Models of Complex Salts for Molten Salt Reactors*, *Thermo.* 1 (2021) 168–178. <https://doi.org/10.3390/thermo1020012>.
- [11] A.D. Pelton, *Phase Diagrams and Thermodynamic Modeling of Solutions*, Elsevier, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2013-0-19504-9>.
- [12] J.-O. Andersson, T. Helander, L. Höglund, P. Shi, B. Sundman, *Thermo-Calc & DICTRA: Computational tools for materials science*, *Calphad.* 26 (2002) 273–312. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0364-5916\(02\)00037-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0364-5916(02)00037-8).
- [13] B. Sundman, U.R. Kattner, M. Palumbo, S.G. Fries, *OpenCalphad - a free thermodynamic software*, *Integr. Mater. Manuf. Innov.* 4 (2015) 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40192-014-0029-1/FIGURES/5>.
- [14] W. Cao, S.-L. Chen, F. Zhang, K. Wu, Y. Yang, Y.A. Chang, R. Schmid-Fetzer, W.A. Oates, *PANDAT software with PanEngine, PanOptimizer and PanPrecipitation for multi-component phase diagram calculation and materials property simulation*, *Calphad.* 33 (2009) 328–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.calphad.2008.08.004>.
- [15] R.A. Otis, Z.-K. Liu, *pycalphad: CALPHAD-based Computational Thermodynamics in Python*, *J. Open Res. Softw.* 5 (2017) 1. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.140>.
- [16] B. Bocklund, R. Otis, A. Egorov, A. Obaied, I. Roslyakova, Z.-K. Liu, *ESPEI for efficient thermodynamic database development, modification, and uncertainty quantification: application to Cu–Mg*, *MRS Commun.* 9 (2019) 618–627. <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrc.2019.59>.
- [17] Scientific Group Thermodata Europe (SGTE), *Molten Salts Database*, (n.d.). <https://www.sgte.net/en/sgte-molten-salt-database-salt>.

- [18] C. Guéneau, N. Dupin, L. Kjellqvist, E. Geiger, M. Kurata, S. Gossé, E. Corcoran, A. Quaini, R. Hania, A.L. Smith, M.H.A. Piro, T. Besmann, P.E.A. Turchi, J.C. Dumas, M.J. Welland, T. Ogata, B.O. Lee, J.R. Kennedy, C. Adkins, M. Bankhead, D. Costa, TAF-ID: An international thermodynamic database for nuclear fuels applications, *Calphad*. 72 (2021) 102212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.calphad.2020.102212>.
- [19] C.W. Bale, E. Bélisle, P. Chartrand, S.A. Deckerov, G. Eriksson, K. Hack, I.-H. Jung, Y.-B. Kang, J. Melançon, A.D. Pelton, C. Robelin, S. Petersen, FactSage thermochemical software and databases — recent developments, *Calphad*. 33 (2009) 295–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.calphad.2008.09.009>.
- [20] M.H.A. Piro, S. Simunovic, T.M. Besmann, B.J. Lewis, W.T. Thompson, The thermochemistry library Thermochemica, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 67 (2013) 266–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2012.09.011>.
- [21] J.C. Ard, J.A. Yingling, K.E. Johnson, J. Schorne-Pinto, M. Aziziha, C.M. Dixon, M.S. Christian, J.W. McMurray, T.M. Besmann, Development of the Molten Salt Thermal Properties Database – Thermochemical (MSTDB–TC), example applications, and LiCl–RbCl and UF₃–UF₄ system assessments, *J. Nucl. Mater.* 563 (2022) 153631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2022.153631>.
- [22] M. Poschmann, P. Bajpai, B.W.N. Fitzpatrick, M.H.A. Piro, Recent developments for molten salt systems in Thermochemica, *Calphad*. 75 (2021) 102341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.calphad.2021.102341>.
- [23] A.D. Pelton, P. Chartrand, G. Eriksson, The modified quasi-chemical model: Part IV. Two-sublattice quadruplet approximation, *Metall. Mater. Trans. A Phys. Metall. Mater. Sci.* 32 (2001) 1409–1416.
- [24] G. Lambotte, P. Chartrand, Thermodynamic optimization of the (Na₂O + SiO₂ + NaF + SiF₄) reciprocal system using the Modified Quasichemical Model in the Quadruplet Approximation, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.* 43 (2011) 1678–1699.
- [25] RELAX NG, (n.d.). <https://relaxng.org/> (accessed April 19, 2022).
- [26] J.A. Ocadiz-Flores, E. Capelli, P.E. Raison, R.J.M. Konings, A.L. Smith, Thermodynamic assessment of the LiF–NiF₂, NaF–NiF₂ and KF–NiF₂ systems, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.* 121 (2018) 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jct.2018.01.023>.
- [27] <https://picalphad.org>, n.d.
- [28] R. Otis, M. Emelianenko, Z.-K. Liu, An improved sampling strategy for global energy minimization of multi-component systems, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 130 (2017) 282–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2017.01.019>.
- [29] N.H. Paulson, B.J. Bocklund, R.A. Otis, Z.-K. Liu, M. Stan, Quantified uncertainty in thermodynamic modeling for materials design, *Acta Mater.* 174 (2019) 9–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2019.05.017>.
- [30] V.T. Kalinnikov, D.V. Makarov, V.I. Skiba, E.L. Tikhomirova, Phase Diagrams of the NaF–NiF₂ and KF–NiF₂ Systems, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.* 44 (1999) 1116–1117.
- [31] G. Wagner, D. Balz, *Berichte der Bunsengesellschaft für physikalische Chemie*, 56 (1952) 574–579.

Figures and Figure Captions:

Figure 1. Examples of three categories of quadruplets. (a) A_2X_2 unary quadruplet, (b) ABX_2 binary quadruplet, and (c) $ABXY$ reciprocal quadruplet. Note that this figure is a reproduction based on Pelton et al.'s work [23].

Figure 2. Flow chart that describes the implementation of MQMQA into the PyCalphad software.

Figure 3. (a) Gibbs energy function, (b) entropy, and (c) enthalpy of the liquid phase in the KF- NiF_2 pseudobinary system as a function of $x(NiF_2)$ at 1600 K. Red symbols are results calculated using PyCalphad, blue using Thermochemica, and green using FactSage. These calculations are based on Ocadiz-Flores's database [26].

Figure 4. Gibbs energy surface of the liquid phase in the KF-NiF₂ pseudobinary system at 1600 K calculated using PyCalphad from Ocadiz-Flores's database [26].

Figure 5. Pseudobinary phase diagram of KF-NiF₂ system plotted along with the experimental datapoints of Ocadiz-Flores, Wagner and Kalinnikov [26].

Figure 6. Quadruplet fractions as a function of $x(\text{NiF}_2)$ at 1600 K in the liquid phase from Ocadiz-Flores's database [26].

Figure 7. Convergence of chains in first 50 MCMC iterations. 800 iterations were run for MCMC. Y axis label '- lnprob' represents the logarithm of the probability with a negative sign to make the value positive. The chains will converge toward larger probabilities, thus -lnprob will decrease.

Figure 8. Parameter uncertainty propagated onto the phase fraction as a function of temperature at $x(\text{NiF}_2)=0.32$. The shaded area represents the 95% high density interval (HDI).

Figure 9. Parameter uncertainty propagated onto the activity as a function of composition at 1800 K. The shaded area represents the 95% HDI.

Tables

Table 1. Commonly used software tools in the CALPHAD community using the TDB and/or the DAT format to describe thermodynamic database. Their features include the implementation of MQMQA or not, equilibrium thermodynamic calculations (Eq-Calc), database development by optimizing phase diagram and thermochemical data (Opt.), uncertainty quantification (UQ), open-source or not (Open), and the key programming languages used. The symbol ✓ indicates the feature included, the symbol * indicates the initial stage of feature development, and the empty indicates the feature is unavailable.

Format	Software	MQMQA	Eq-Calc	Opt.	Open	UQ	Languages
TDB	Thermo-Calc						Fortran
	Pandat						C/C++
	OpenCalphad	✓	*	*	✓		Fortran
TDB, DAT, XML	PyCalphad/ESPEI	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Python
DAT	FactSage and ChemSage	✓	✓	✓			VB, Fortran, etc.
	Thermochimica	✓	✓		✓		Fortran

*Not released to the public.

Table 2. Gibbs energy parameters of liquid in the KF-NiF₂ system after 800 MCMC iterations, compared with the initial values from Ocadiz-Flores et al. [26].

Parameter values	Reference
$\Delta g_{\text{KNi:F}_2}^{\text{ex}} = -17062.4 - 13654.3\chi_{\text{NiK/F}_2}$	This work after 800 MCMC iterations
$\Delta g_{\text{KNi:F}_2}^{\text{ex}} = -17573 - 15899\chi_{\text{NiK/F}_2}$	Ocadiz-Flores et al. [26]

Supplemental Materials

NOTE THAT the mentioned files can be found in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6471272>

Table S1. Folder and files name of List

Folder/File	Notes
pycalphad	A folder with Jupyter notebook example and files for using PyCalphad for equilibrium calculations.
ESPEI	A folder with Jupyter notebook example and files for using ESPEI for modeling optimization.
Installation.md	File with instruction for installation of PyCalphad/ESPEI

Table S2. Explanation of the Jupyter notebook “MQMQA-DEMO.ipynb” in folder “pycalphad”.

Item	Comments and notes	
Purpose	To perform equilibrium calculations for system modelled with MQMQA using PyCalphad, including phase diagrams, Gibbs energy, etc.	
Input files	Ocadiz_combined.dat	KF-NiF ₂ database from Ocadiz-Flores et al., DOI: 10.1016/j.jct.2018.01.023
	MSTDB_test.dat	MSTDB from T. Besmann et al., DOI: 10.1016/j.jnucmat.2022.153631
Output files	MSTDB.xml	MSTDB in XML format.

Table S3. Explanation of the Jupyter notebook “MCMC-DEMO.ipynb” in folder “ESPEI”.

Item	Comments and notes	
Purpose	To perform optimization of system with MQMQA using ESPEI, databases are in XML format.	
Input files	input_data	Subfolder containing experimental data of KF-NiF ₂ system summarized by Ocadiz-Flores et al., DOI: 10.1016/j.jct.2018.01.023.
	ESPEI_demo.yaml	Setting file for EPSEI running in yaml format.
	Ocadiz_combined.dat	KF-NiF ₂ database from Ocadiz-Flores et al., DOI: 10.1016/j.jct.2018.01.023.
	Ocadiz_combined.xml	Ocadiz_combined.dat converted into XML format. Note that the adjustable parameters (starting from VV..) should be set before running MCMC; see details in https://espei.org .
	Phases.json	JSON file to specify models of phases in the database.
Output files	MCMC_demo.xml	Output database after MCMC optimization.
	Inprob_demo.npy	File recording probability of chains during MCMC.
	trace_demo.npy	Trace file for MCMC.